

**Introducing sustainable agroforestry to encourage implementation of social forestry in
Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit, Lampung, Indonesia**

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ABSTRACT

To ensure sustainability of livelihood and community access in forest land management through Social Forestry Program, sustainable agroforestry system has to be applied. Social Forestry in Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit (FMU) has performed through forestry partnership scheme, although the activity is still in the form of monoculture agriculture. The research aimed to initiate application of sustainable agroforestry technology in Gedong Wani FMU involving surrounding forest community. The research used experimental method by establishing a 2 ha participatory demonstration plot at Kandis Resort. The research stages include socialization of sustainable agroforestry concept, structured interview about community perception on agroforestry practice and their preference on plant species, survey on biophysical aspect of the site, construction of technical design, seed(lings) preparation and transplanting of the seed(lings). The results showed that communities at the research site have never received socialization on sustainable agroforestry concept yet. Respondent preference on plant species were influenced by market prospect and fulfillment on food and wood. In the demonstration plot area, there were rubber plants with 66 trees/ha density with only 19% shading capacity. Its land cover was 8.76% and basal area was 0.82 m²/ha. Soil fertility at the demonstration plot was categorized very low; especially its contents of Nitrogen, Phosphor and Potassium, so high production inputs are needed. Farmers' participation was high, especially in the stages of technical design construction, land preparation and seed(lings) planting activities. Establishment of sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot at Kandis Resort is expected could encourage acceleration of Social Forestry implementation throughout Gedong Wani FMU areas.

Keywords: *Demonstration plot, farmer preference, plant species, sustainable agroforestry*

INTRODUCTION

Social Forestry Program was launched by Ministry of Forestry in 2002 to promote community-based forest management (Nawir et al. 2007). According

to the Minister of Environmental and Forestry Decree no. 83/2016, Social Forestry is a sustainable forest management system in state or private or customary forest areas conducted by local or customary law communities as main actors to enhance their welfare, environment balancing and social-culture dynamic. There are some schemes of Social Forestry Program implemented in the state forest area, namely Village Forest, Community Forest, People Plantation Forest and Forestry Partnership (Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan 2016). To enhance opportunity for surrounding forest community in managing the forest, Indonesian Government has allocated 12.7 million ha of forest area to be managed under Social Forestry Program (Kabinet Kerja 2014). However, implementation of the program was not sufficient yet although it has supported by some legal umbrellas such as Government Regulation, Ministry Decree and Directorate General Decree. So far, realization of Social Forestry Program is still low (Praputra et al. 2015). Supriyanto (2018) reported that as per September 2nd 2018 the forest areas which were managed under the program are still 1.85 million ha. One of constrains faced in development of the program is community capacity in preparing forest management still low. Therefore, community empowerment program such as establishment of sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot should be conducted. Demonstration plot is a field extension method to show or to prove in real condition that application of a technology is benefit for community.

Empowerment program is an incentive scheme to attracting and maintaining participation in community based natural resource management initiatives. Giles et al. (2014) argued that financial incentive intervention was significantly effective for encouraging community behavior change as expected. Incentive which is meant to modify behavior can in some cases be cost effective (Gneezy et al. 2011).

Today, agroforestry has carved out a distinct niche as a robust land-management discipline, and it is now recognized as being at the heart of the global community's commitment to banish hunger and poverty and rebuild resilient rural environments (Nair and Garrity 2012). Furthermore, Garrity (2012) stated that the future of land use across the world faces many stark challenges, namely food security, land degradation, desperate poverty, climate change, and others. But agroforesters have tools to address many of them in an integrated and practical way.

Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit (FMU) is located in South Lampung District, Lampung Province, Indonesia where the forest areas are in degraded conditions. Generally, the forest areas have encroached by surrounding communities. There are two sub districts and 39 definitive villages existed in the forest areas, including buildings of local governments, schools and

community houses. Land cover is dominated by monoculture agriculture, shrubs, estate crop plantation, open areas and settlements. Social Forestry in Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit (FMU) has performed through forestry partnership scheme. However, the activity is still in the form of monoculture agriculture. Actually, agroforestry systems are common features of Indonesian natural landscape. Unfortunately, these mixed species systems are increasingly being replaced by monoculture agriculture. This condition also occurred in the Indian state of Kerala. Guillerme et al. (2011) reported that the existing sectoral policies of land tenure, agriculture, and forestry contributed to promoting monoculture crops plantation, even among marginal farmers. The research aimed to initiate application of sustainable agroforestry technology in Gedong Wani FMU involving surrounding forest community in order to encourage implementation of Social Forestry throughout the FMU areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Site and Time

The research was conducted at Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit (FMU), South Lampung District, Lampung Province, Indonesia, during 2017. The research was done in Karang Rejo Village, Jati Agung Sub District which is located at Kandis Resort with coordinate 05°14,25' South Latitude, 105°23,03' East Longitude and elevation is 72 m asl (Fig. 1). The Karang Rejo Village has 1,370 HH with population was 5,346 persons (UPTD KPHP Gedong Wani, 2016). Main livelihood of the community is dry land farming with main food crops are corn, cassava and paddy, and tree crop is rubber.

Source: <https://petatematikindo.wordpress.com/2016/02/02/administrasi-kabupaten-lampung-selatan>
 Figure 1. Map of the research site, Karang Rejo Village, Jati Agung Sub District, South Lampung District, Lampung Province, Indonesia (● is a research site)

Data Collection

Definitive research site was determined through a series of discussion with the officials of Forestry Services of Lampung Province, Lampung University and Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit. The research used experimental method by establishing a 2 ha participatory demonstration plot. The research stages include socialization of sustainable agroforestry concept, structured interview about community perception on agroforestry practice and their preference on plant species, survey on biophysical aspect of the site, construction of technical design, seed(lings) preparation and transplanting of the seed(lings) to the field.

The target group of the socialization and structured interview is all members of Agro Forest Park Forest Farmer Group (KTH Agro Forest Park). There are 27 persons of the KTH Agro Forest Park member. Survey on biophysical aspects on the demonstration plot area including identifying and measuring population of existing vegetation, shading capacity, land cover, basal area and soil fertility.

Data on light intensity on the ground or shading capacity of existing vegetation at an agroforestry demonstration plot is important to be identified. Thus data could be used to determine planting pattern and which plant species should be planted, both timber tree and tree producing food as well as annual food crops. Light intensity at the agroforestry demonstration plot was measured by using a lux meter at three different times, in the morning about 09.00 o'clock, at noon (12.00 o'clock) and at afternoon (15.00 o'clock). In order to calculate basal area and land cover of existing vegetation at the demonstration plot, stem diameter and crown diameter of all trees were measured.

Soil samples were collected thoroughly according to the diagonal lines of the plot at depth of 20 and 40 cm. Further, the samples were analyzed at Laboratory of Research Institute for Spices and Medicine (Balai Penelitian Rempah dan Obat/BALITRO) in Bogor. Technical design of the demonstration plot was constructed participatively involving all members of the KTH Agro Forest Park. Activities of seed(ling) preparation and the seed(lings) transplanting to the field were also done participatively. Level of farmer participation was determined based on number of the farmer present in each activity.

Data analysis

Farmer preference data on plant species were tabulated. Data on biophysical conditions of the demonstration plot were tabulated and calculated and then described quantitatively and qualitatively. Result of soil samples

analysis was discussed descriptively as well as level of farmer participation in activities during establishment of the demonstration plot.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Forestry Partnership Scheme in Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit

Forestry partnership is one of the Social Forestry schemes to empowerment surrounding forest community as stated in Minister of Environment and Forestry Decree No. 83/2016 on Social Forestry. The regulation mandate to manage certain forest areas with forestry partnership as media for conflict resolutions on forest resource which was usually happened between forest manager and the surrounding forest communities. Jasuli (2014) mentioned that partnership as a form of alliance between two or more parties which make a band of cooperation based on agreement with the same objectives in order to achieve better results.

One of the forestry partnership in managing the forest area of Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit (FMU) is a forestry partnership between the Gedong Wani FMU and Forest Farmer Group of Agro Forest Park (KTH Agro Forest Park) The partnership was declared through establishment certificate No. 20 in December 2014 with the objectives are to increase forest cover, food production and the community income.

Farmer perception on sustainable agroforestry and their preference to the plant species

Socialization activity to the member of KTH Agro Forest Park at the research site aims to introduce sustainable or throughout tree cycle agroforestry concept and to explore farmer interest in establishing the agroforestry demonstration plot. The result showed that most of the farmers have not understood yet about sustainable agroforestry technique and they have not believed yet about government commitment on Social Forestry Program. However, they have high interest to participate in establishing the sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot on the forest land where they do crops cultivation during this time. Based on these facts, it is urgent to enhance farmers' knowledge through convene socialization events and establishment of demonstration plots at many places in order to accelerate farmer's adoption on agroforestry technology. Seline *et al.* (2015) mentioned that community's knowledge, attitude and perception play a key role in making a decision to adopt or not a new technology in relation to its advantages and challenges.

Education level of most the KTH member (59%) was only Primary School with main livelihood are as farmer or farm worker (96%) (Table 1). The

forest lands were managed as dry land monoculture agriculture (*ladang*) and home garden. They cultivate food crops such as corn, paddy and cassava at *ladang* and some fruit trees (like mango, longan, *petai*, coconut, jackfruit and banana) and vegetables (as chili, eggplant, tubers and spices) at home garden. Most of farmer income obtained from dry land farming production, while home garden yield only utilized for farmer household consumption.

Interview on plant species which is preferred to be developed in the demonstration plot showed that 72 % of respondent select teak (*Tectona grandis*) for the timber tree, 59 % of them choose *petai* (*Parkia speciosa*) for tree crop (tree producing food) and for food crop 55% of them choose corn (*Zea mays*), 41% cassava and 14% select paddy (*Oryza sativa*) (Table 2). Main farmer considerations in the plant species selection were market prospect or the product is easy to sell and it can be utilized directly to fulfill their need on wood and food.

Table 1. Social and economy condition of Agro Forest Park Forest Farmer Group, Karang Rejo Village, Jati Agung Sub District

No.	Characteristic of Respondent	Classification	Number of Respondent	Percentage (%)
1	Age (year)	20 – 30	1	3.70
		31 – 40	1	3.70
		41 – 50	13	48.15
		51 – 60	7	25.93
		>60	5	18.52
2	Formal Education	Never went to school	1	3.70
		Primary School	16	59.26
		Junior High School	7	25.93
		Senior High School	3	11.11
3	Main job	Farmer/farm worker	26	96.30
		Trader and other services	1	3.70
4	Size of forest land governance (ha)	≤ 0,25	1	3.70
		0,26 - 0,50	6	22.22
		0,51 - 0,75	5	18.52
		0,76 - 1	5	18.52
		> 1	10	37.04

Table 2. Farmer preferences on plant species to be developed in the demonstration plot in Karang Rejo Village, Jati Agung Sub District, South Lampung District

Type of plant	First choice		Second choice		Third choice	
	Species	Percentage (%)	Species	Percentage (%)	Species	Percentage (%)
Timber tree	Teak (<i>Tectona grandis</i>)	72	Sengon (<i>Falcataria moluccana</i>)	36	-	-
Tree crop (tree producing food)	Petai (<i>Parkia speciosa</i>)	59	Sirsak (<i>Annona muricata</i>)	22	Jackfruit (<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>)	18
Food crop	Corn (<i>Zea mays</i>)	55	Cassava (<i>Manihot esculenta</i>)	41	Paddy (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	14

Biophysical condition of the demonstration plot area

There were rubber trees on the area with about 3.5 years old and planting spacing is 5m x 3m. However, its population was very low, only 66 trees/ha. Most of them were died and some others were coppiced by the farmer. Since population of rubber tree was very low and some of them have no canopy, average shading capacity of the trees were also low, i.e. 19.2% or average light intensity that can be arrive on the ground was high namely 80.8%. It means that there is a big opportunity to plant some tree and food crops species at the agroforestry demonstration plot. Data on rubber trees characteristic as existing vegetations at the agroforestry demonstration plot are presented at Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of rubber tree at the agroforestry demonstration plot in Karang Rejo Village, Jati Agung Sub District, South Lampung District

Characteristic	Value	Characteristic	Value
Density (tree/ha)	66	Average shading capacity (%)	19.2
Average stem diameter (cm)	10.1	Average light intensity (%)	80.8
Average crown diameter (cm)	389.7	Average land cover (%)	8.8
Basal Area (m ² /ha)	0.82		

Result of soil sample analysis is presented at Table 4. The soil was slightly acid with average pH value was 5.75. Level of the soil fertility was determined according to assessment criteria created by Balai Penelitian Tanah

(2005). Based on those criteria, soil fertility at agroforestry demonstration plot was very low, all soil fertility variable were classified into very low criteria except C/N ratio. In order to achieve sustainable farming at the area, the nutrient content of the soil, especially soil organic matter, should be enhanced through providing of organic manure.

Table 4. Soil fertility at agroforestry demonstration plot in Karang Rejo Village, Jati Agung Sub District, South Lampung District

No. of Sample & depth	pH (H ₂ O)	C _{org} (%)	N _{total} (%)	C/N	P _{available} (ppm)	P _{total} (mg /100g)	K _{available} (cmol/kg)	K _{total} (mg/100g)	CEC (cmol /kg)
1 ₂₀	5,78	1,13	0,09	12,6	0,42	10	0,04	2	4,46
2 ₂₀	5,96	1,07	0,10	10,7	0,57	15	0,23	2	4,59
3 ₂₀	5,57	1,06	0,08	13,3	2,88	27	0,09	6	4,27
Average	5,77	1,09	0,09	12,2	1,29	17,3	0,12	3,3	4,44
1 ₄₀	5,74	1,02	0,06	17,1	1,78	7	0,04	2	4,29
2 ₄₀	5,74	0,83	0,08	10,4	2,52	9	0,04	2	4,65
3 ₄₀	5,72	0,68	0,08	8,5	1,85	16	0,09	4	4,68
Average	5,73	0,84	0,07	12	2,05	10,7	0,06	2,7	4,54
Total	5,75	0,97	0,08	12,1	1,67	14,0	0,09	3,0	4,49
Average Criteria	SA	VL	VL	M	VL	VL	VL	VL	VL

Remark: SA (Slightly Acid); M (Moderate); VL (Very Low)

Technical design of sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot

Technical design of sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot was constructed participatively with all farmers involved. The technical design covers planting pattern and plant species which would be planted in the demonstration plot. There were three types of plant planted at the demonstration plot, namely teak (*Tectona grandis*) for timber tree, petai (*Parkia speciosa*) for tree crop and black paddy for annual food crop for first season only. Despite teak wood is expensive, but it is favored wood and many people are looking for the wood. In Indonesia, the tree usually grow at lowland up to hilly places with elevation 700 m asl (Adinugraha *et al.* 2014). Therefore, farmers, who planting teak trees has a big opportunity and good market prospect to earn benefit. *Petai* (*Parkia speciosa* Hassk) is a plant that grows originally in tropical region, like Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand and Philippine (Kamisah *et al.* 2013). It has an open crown, so it suitable to be cultivated in agroforestry systems. *Petai* has high utilization value as source of food and industry raw material as well as for medicine (Mulyono 2013). Kamisah *et al.* (2013) reported that *P. speciosa* contains much nutritional value and anti-oxidant compound, so that it has a potency to be developed as phyto-medicine.

There were two types of planting pattern applied at the demonstration plot in order to gain difference shading effect and to examine growth and production of various estate and food crops which would be planted subsequently as lower stratum of agroforestry component (Figure 2). First is rectangular pattern, its mean that *petai* was planted inside plot with planting distance 7.5m x 10m in rectangular form, while teak was only planted at the border of the plot with spacing 5 m in between. Second is pentagonal pattern, means that *petai* was planted with spacing 7.5m x 5m in pentagonal form, while teak was also planted at the border only with the same spacing (5 m in between).

Planting distance among tree components is designed wider; it is intended to provide more space and time for planting herbaceous plants between the tree rows. Thus, farmer access and income from the agroforestry plot will be accelerated and sustainable.

Remark: ● : Teak (*Tectona grandis*), ▲ : Petai (*Parkia*)

Figure 2. Two planting patterns applied at sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot with wider spacing among the tree component

Establishment of sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot

Establishment of sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot was performed based on the technical design which was constructed and agreed among the farmers involved. The activities were started with area measurement, plot boundary installation and land preparation. Furthermore, planting line and planting hole were made according to the planting pattern, each planting hole was provided with organic manure with dosage 1 kg/hole. Teak and *petai* seedlings were transplanted to the planting hole about 2 weeks after; followed by planting of black paddy seeds. Finally, signboard of the demonstration plot was installed.

Farmers' participation in establishing the agroforestry demonstration plot was assessed based on their attendance at each stage of activity. The assessment was indicated that farmers' participation was high, especially in the stages of technical design construction, land preparation and seed(lings) planting activities. Khan *et al.* (2009) stated that demonstration plots were not only successful in creating awareness among farmers about modern technologies but also motivated them to apply it in their farming practices. Moreover, farmers participated in the demonstration plot activities to gain practical know-how about improved farming practices. These have resulted in increased productivity and income of the farmers.

CONCLUSIONS

Sustainable agroforestry demonstration plot as field extension media to farmer has established in forest area of Gedong Wani Forest Management Unit, South Lampung District. This is to initiate application of sustainable agroforestry technology in order to support Social Forestry Program in Indonesia. The demonstration plot was performed through a series of activities involving surrounding community. Biophysical condition of the demonstration plot, especially soil fertility is categorized very low with pH value was slightly acid. Farmers' participation in establishing the demonstration plot was high, especially in the stages of technical design construction, land preparation and seed(lings) planting activities.

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